

UNIVERSITI BRUNEI DARUSSALAM

2020/2021

BM-5102

Reflective Report

For

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BM-5102 Organizational Behaviour

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Introduction

I graduated with an honours as a Business Administration student in Universiti Brunei Darussalam(UBD). When I graduated from the University, I immediately knew I needed to pursue a postgraduate degree in Masters of Management in Brunei Darussalam. I am an enthusiastic person as I already have my goals and objectives set in my mind, which includes to secure a place to be manager in an executive management level either in public or private sectors. But, I personally prefer to secure a place at the executive management level in the public sector. This has been inspiring me to continue my postgraduate education in Masters of Management in Brunei Darussalam. This is with the hope for me to improve my education, experience and level of understanding in being a better manager/leader in the future.

Being a manager is really amazing for the right person. Personally, this is because being a manager is amazing, I can witness my team members grow and develop their skills and experience. This is the feeling that excites me in knowing that I have been in the process that helped them to develop further as they work with me. I have always seen the responsibility of being a manager as an opportunity to help me build my leadership skills, it can be theoretically or physically. UBD has been providing amazing courses over the period of studies I am in when I was a Bachelor Degree student. With the help of the Organizational Behaviour module in the course of my Masters of Management Degree, helps me to identify the differences between being a leader and a manager. I have taken Organizational Behaviour once in my degree course, and now in my masters degree course. What I understand in being a leader, is to always inspire other members, however for a manager, they manages others.

Therefore, in being enrolled in this Organizational Behaviour I was hoping to hone my skills, experience - theoretically and physically to develop my strength to be employable. This will be an added bonus to boost resume as having the title of a manager can help boost credibility with other employers as well as in the professional networks.

However, in the course of my masters of management modules, I have encountered an interesting topic that was offered by Dr. Pg. Siti Rozaidah, which we did a group project study based on systematic literature review on *Halal Education, Training and Development: Issues and Challenges*. The systematic literature study that our team has produced, reflected a very good teamwork and excellently done. Our group find the topic very interesting because of how Brunei Darussalam is always associated with having strong islamic practices in which Brunei has always been rooted back to the teachings on Melayu Islam Beraja and Syariah Law as the base of living.

Halal Education, Training, and Development: Issues and Challenges (Group Project Overview)

Halal industry has been increasingly accepted globally. The market for halal industry has managed to capture the eyes of those that are muslims and non-muslims. With the increasing acceptance among the non-muslim consumers, the halal industry has been expanding globally. According to Global Halal Industry (2020), the halal industry was estimated to be worth around USD2.3 trillion at a growing rate of 20% annually worldwide. And also because of the growing numbers of muslims worldwide which is estimated to be 1.8 billion total of the population of muslims globally. This has been capturing our interest in looking into the halal industry in the context of Brunei Darussalam. This is because Brunei

Darussalam actually can have the opportunity to be the pioneer in Halal industry globally. This is because Brunei's government has been making efforts in keeping halal industry in Brunei to flourish. According to one research paper published in Brunei on looking at overview of Halal industry in Brunei, she mentioned that researchers are being aware regarding the growing market of halal industry globally, and this gives an opportunity for Brunei to diversify the Halal industry market (Raihana, 2019). Therefore, this has triggered my team's interest in exploring the new possibilities of Halal industry in Brunei in order for Brunei to diversify the halal market globally.

The targeted objectives of our project were to compile and discuss different issues and challenges focusing on halal education, development and training. We focused on Halal industry areas because there was less research done in Brunei Darussalam regarding this matter. Halal industry in Brunei can be improved more by examining the views of different scholars, as for example in Organizational Behavior, in regards to productions, distribution, marketing etc. I have attempted to collect a total of at least seven articles and thoroughly read all of the articles to pick and match relevant information to be included in the paper. We have divided our work accordingly in order to achieve the targeted objectives of our systematic literature paper. Since we have a total of four people in our group, we have decided to collect at least 7 articles at least for each member to dissect the academic papers and do thorough research about Halal. The requirements of doing systematic literature review is very lengthy actually, but my group, we have tried our best to collect as many article journals as possible, but the time seems to beat us even before we can collect more than 30 article journals.

Mallett, Hagen-Zanker, Slater & Duvenzack (2012), mentioned that a systematic literature review required an access to an extensive range of databases. This also means that extensive learning requires more time to do thorough studies and time consuming.

Halal Industry Logistics - Education, Training and Development in Brunei Darussalam

In the literature review study that we have identified that the issues in Brunei Darussalam industry are not according to the Halal awareness, education and development solely, but rather the logistics area on: training of personnel, lacking of professionals in the field and the lengthy processes that the logistics-wise taking in halal production and logistics. Since, there were only few experimental research studies that have only been done in Brunei Darussalam, potential researchers may have this advantage in looking into the logistics criteria which can help to improve Halal industry in Brunei better. According to one research, they mentioned that Halal logistics chains can help to improve and foster growth of new businesses in Brunei Darussalam and lead Brunei's economic stability (Syazwan, & Abu Bakar, 2015). In the future, I would like to see the overview of Halal logistics in Brunei, then consult professionals in the Halal logistics area to assess future improvements to be made in Brunei.

Also, halal industry in Brunei can help to elevate the issues of unemployment. According to Hayat, with halal market booming globally, it is hoped that the government intervention will collaborate with relevant agencies to equip Brunei's population in providing knowledge and expertise required (Musa & Idris, 2020). Hence, with the research studies that we have done, I hope to provide ample knowledge in helping the government to improve Halal industry in Brunei Darussalam.

Outcome of the Module and Semester

After taking the module, I have a clearer image on what organizational behavior is all about. It is the study of human behavior within the organization. This refers to understanding how people and groups are behaving, communicating - all of this is being examined in order to shape the behavior of the organization to achieve their targeted objectives. This has helped me so far into giving me the overview in looking into the corporate world, by having this giving me a high degree of understanding on how the corporate world works. With proper organizational behavior would help an organization to gain a competitive advantage over others, through improved leadership, motivation, communication and organizational culture. I have realised that, with the given group topic project that we have done, we can help to improve Halal industry in Brunei Darussalam, through improving the organizational behavior and the management. This is currently what is lacking in the terms of Halal Industry Brunei's organization. I hope the information that we have gathered and systematic literature review that we have done will help to provide more insights and see issues more in depth to provide future solutions.

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